

ISic1529

I.Sicily inscription 1529

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 88

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Staurogram in the centre of the inscription that crosses the whole text, cuts in half δ of Καλανδίωνος, completes the letter π of τόπος and ends with two leaves symmetrical to it.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Καλα[ν]δῖωνος

2. τόπος

2a.

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645029

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.33
Ferrua, A 1938-1939. Note di epigrafia cristiana siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 4-5: 19-37. At no.88

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